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Advanced FTIR spectroscopic techniques for analyzing microplastics in biological samples: Preliminary results and method comparison in stool samples

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Analyzing microplastics (MPs) in biological samples is critical for assessing exposure risks and potential health impacts. This task is challenging due to the complex physicochemical properties of MPs. Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy is widely used method for analyzing microplastics, but manual selection of particles for FTIR analysis is prone to human bias.

This study compares manual, semi-automated, and automated FTIR methods for identifying MPs in stool samples, focusing on analysis duration, types of detected polymers, abundance, and average size of microplastics.

Manual analysis involved single-point analysis using microFTIR in reflective mode. Automated particle analysis was conducted using OMNIC Picta Software. Semi-automated analysis utilized chemical mapping, collecting approximately 200,000 spectra with an ultrafast mapping mode using a linear array detector. Acceptable spectrum-matching accuracy was over 60%, varying by polymer type. Semi-automated analysis required manual verification to ensure detected polymers matched the reference spectrum (recovery rate $98 \pm 7\%$), while automated analysis relied on Particle Wizard software (recovery rate $85 \pm 17\%$). Manual analysis (5 ± 4 min per point) did not cover the entire filter area. Semi-automated analysis ($\sim 4 \pm 0.5$ h) was faster than automated analysis ($> 8 \pm 0.9$ h) for the whole filter area (1 mm^2). Automated analysis sometimes missed particles due to small intensity differences relative to the background, causing underestimation. Semi-automated analysis allowed manual checking of suspect particles, providing more reliable results.

Differences observed using the same instrument highlight the challenge of standardizing MP analysis and the need for cross-validation among various methods and instruments.

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